

NEW INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES

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Abstract. The need to modernize Uzbek education, integration into the pan-European educational space, preservation and development of the best traditions of the national school makes significant adjustments to the education system for schoolchildren. Modern society needs educated, qualified specialists, distinguished by mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, true patriots of their homeland, respecting the culture, scientific achievements, traditions of other countries and peoples. In this regard, the concept of humanization of socio-economic relations was adopted, where the main role is given to the modernization of Uzbek education. Orientation towards humanistic ideals presupposes the priority of the interests of the individual, the creation of a creative atmosphere in learning and ensuring the general cultural development of students. The most important part of the educational process is the personality-oriented interaction between the teacher and the student, which requires changing the main trends and improving educational technologies. It is the study of foreign languages that can be considered as one of the most important means of humanizing and humanitarizing education.

Key words: society, innovative, technologies, educational

In the information society, knowledge and qualifications become of primary importance in human life. To keep abreast of the development of world science, it is necessary to study primary sources in the language of the authors. Therefore, the increasing importance of a foreign language and its demand have influenced the content, objectives and dynamics of learning. In the 21st century, the intensification and modernization of education requires the introduction of innovative technologies that pursue the goal of creative education of the individual in the intellectual and emotional dimensions. Such innovative technologies are: developmental learning, design, problem-based learning, level differentiation, test system, game learning, immersion in a foreign language culture, collaborative learning, self-education and autonomy, integration, as well as health-preserving, research, information and communication and personal development. oriented technologies. With such a target setting, cognitive universal actions are one of the leading components of the educational standard. This is explained by the fact that one of the components of a child's mental development is his cognition, which implies the formation of a scientific picture of the world, the ability to manage his intellectual activity, mastery of methodology, strategies and methods of learning, the development of

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representative, symbolic, logical, creative thinking, productive imagination, memory, attention, reflection. In this regard, cognitive universal actions include:

- actions to extract information;
- the ability to navigate the knowledge system and realize the need for new knowledge;
- the ability to make a preliminary selection of information sources to search for new knowledge.

Problem-based learning technology involves independent solving cognitive and creative problems through critical rethinking and augmentation of knowledge and skills; and allows for the implementation of the conditions for the formation of cognitive universal actions in students: creating an atmosphere of co-creation in communication, inclusion of the child's emotional sphere, personal interest of the student, joint search for truth, self-assessment, self-correction, self-sufficiency.

One of the ways to activate students in the process of teaching foreign languages is design (project method), when the student independently plans, creates, and defends his project, i.e. actively involved in the process of communicative activity. An educational project is a complex of search, research, calculation, graphic and other types of work performed by students independently for the purpose of practical or theoretical solution to a significant problem.

The main goals of the project methodology are:

- 1) self-expression and self-improvement of students, increasing learning motivation, developing cognitive interest;
- 2) implementation in practice of acquired skills and abilities, speech development, the ability to competently and reasonably present the research material, and conduct debate;
- 3) demonstrate the level of culture, education, social maturity.

Types of projects:

- 1) role-playing games, dramatizations, dramatizations (fairy tales, TV shows, holidays, musical performances, etc.)
- 2) research (country studies, generalization of scientific knowledge, historical, environmental, etc.)
- 3) creative (essays) , translation, scripts, wall newspapers, etc.)
- 4) multimedia presentations.

What sources of information are usually used when preparing a project?

- a) Books; b) Periodicals; in Internet; d) Teacher; e) Others

The project method helps to develop linguistic and intellectual abilities, a sustainable interest in learning a language, and the need for self-education.

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Ultimately, it is expected to achieve communicative competence, i.e., a certain level of linguistic, regional, sociocultural knowledge, communication skills and speech skills that allow foreign language communication.

The implementation of project and research methods in practice leads to a change in the teacher's position. From a carrier of ready-made knowledge, he turns into an organizer of cognitive activity, as shown in the diagram. From an authoritative source of information, the teacher becomes an accomplice in the research, creative cognitive process, a mentor, a consultant, and an organizer of students' independent activities. Analyzing the use of the project method in a modern school, I believe that this is one of the most powerful incentives for motivating the study of foreign languages, the most creative type of activity, since all students are involved in working on the project, regardless of abilities and level of language training. They put into practice the acquired knowledge and developed speech skills and abilities, creatively rethinking and multiplying. In addition, the problematic nature and variety of forms and types of this technology presupposes the presence of interdisciplinary connections, which allows the student to give a vivid idea of the world in which he lives, the relationship of phenomena and objects, mutual assistance, and the diversity of material and artistic culture. The main emphasis is on the development of imaginative thinking, on understanding cause-and-effect relationships and the logic of events, on self-realization and self-expression not only of students, but also of teachers. The project methodology requires careful preparation, professional skill, and erudition from the teacher. One of the main conditions for the effectiveness of educational activities is an atmosphere of goodwill, mutual understanding, trust, creativity, and encouraging the cognitive activity of schoolchildren.

In the modern understanding, an educational project is an integrated didactic means of development, training and education, which allows you to develop and develop specific skills:

- 1) problematization,
- 2) planning,
- 3) self-analysis and reflection,
- 4) presentation,
- 5) research work.

The use of project methodology is one of the components of the humanization of the educational process, since students with different levels of language training participate in work in accordance with their capabilities. In my opinion, along with group projects, it is necessary to use individual assignments, especially when preparing final lessons - this is a unique opportunity for truly communicative

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teaching of a foreign language. Such lessons relieve stress and fatigue of students, sharply increase cognitive interest, develop students' imagination, thinking, speech, memory, and can be taught on almost any topic within the framework of the program material.

Using the design methodology, the following tasks are solved:

- students' horizons are expanded,
- lexical and grammatical material is consolidated,
- and the teacher creates a methodological collection on various topics with presentations and video projects.

Thus, the project method makes it possible to implement not only educational tasks, but also sociocultural, educational, tasks of humanization and humanitarization of the educational process.

The results are obvious: this technique makes it possible to study the topic in depth, develop the creative abilities of students, teaches communication, the ability to use grammatical structures, and the fear of conducting a conversation in a foreign language disappears. In addition, project technology is effective and exciting for teachers, as it helps them to reveal themselves as creative individuals who participate in research work along with their students. Of course, the project is not a panacea for all problems, but it is a step forward in teaching a foreign language.

Information and communication technologies are a powerful tool for teaching, monitoring and managing the educational process, as it is the most important parameter of the modern sociocultural system. Internet resources are a familiar and convenient means of getting to know the culture of other countries and peoples, communicating, obtaining information, and an inexhaustible source of the educational process. That is why, the basis of a systematic approach to reforming methods of teaching a foreign language using new information technologies is the concept of an information and learning environment, which is considered in close connection with the system of developmental education. The information-learning environment is a set of conditions that not only allow the formation and development of language knowledge, abilities and skills, but also contribute to the development of the student's personality. The educational situation is designed in such an environment as a dynamic process of subjective interaction of all participants in the educational process, mediated by computer technology. The learner, with more and more active, deep and comprehensive participation in the process of independent learning activities for mastering a foreign language, turns from a passive object of the teacher's influence into a full participant in the educational process. The pedagogical relevance of the system of linguistic knowledge and skills formed in the information-learning environment is that the learner should be offered for mastering

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exactly the system of knowledge that he needs at this stage of his development, which subsequently makes it possible to solve problems of increasing complexity.

The tasks of IOS for learning a foreign language:

- providing conditions for the creative development of writing, as well as speech skills;
- integration of various forms and strategies aimed at developing independent cognitive learning activities in the process of individual and group work of students;
- increasing the motivational richness of the educational process
- organizing cognitive communication activities with native speakers and members of the online community learning a foreign language;
- formation on the basis of linguistic knowledge of a modern information culture that allows working in a computer and telecommunications environment.

This innovative technology is based on principles that reflect the specifics of the subject being studied and the learning environment itself: openness, integrativeness, systematicity and consistency, interactivity, clarity of presentation of the material, multidimensionality and redundancy of all components of the environment.

The effective functioning of IES depends on: the level of development of the information and telecommunications infrastructure of education and the interaction of this infrastructure with students; from a whole complex of psychological and pedagogical conditions; from control of the motivational background and its development; taking into account the individual characteristics of students; from the linguistic co-creation of all participants in the educational process.

Structurally, IOS is organized in the form of a model, which is a set of subjects participating in the learning process, the connections between which are realized using information flows, organized in accordance with the goals and objectives of the educational process into functional blocks. Each of the blocks (program-training, information-methodological, communication, instrumental, sociocultural, motivational and identification-controlling) is aimed at implementing strategies for mastering a foreign language, as well as monitoring the progress of the educational process. The environment is in constant development, which is determined by the dynamics of the inclusion of new forms and pedagogical technologies of teaching a foreign language, as well as the development of the participants in the process themselves.

Participation in information and communication pedagogical activities contributes to the comprehensive formation of all aspects of communicative competence: linguistic, sociocultural, cognitive, linguistic and cultural studies; as well as related communicative and cognitive skills of students (search and selection

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of relevant information, its analysis, generalization and classification). Modeling a real authentic environment through the use of Internet resources not only serves to more successfully master the language, but also allows one to comprehend the deep law of the unity and diversity of culture.

Thus, the innovative technologies that we have considered today significantly enrich and diversify the teaching of foreign languages. Monotonous work is replaced by intellectual creative search, during which a new type of personality is formed, active and purposeful, focused on constant self-education and development.

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